

INFLUENCE OF TUMOR MICROENVIRONMENT ON ANGIOGENESIS IN BREAST CANCER

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Purpose: to study the features of tumor angiogenesis and its relationship with the microenvironment in breast cancer.

Materials and methods. To improve the diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer by studying the microenvironment of the tumor, its influence on the course and prognosis, we analyzed a group of 457 patients with breast cancer who were examined and treated at the INKHA University Hospital (South Korea) (362 patients) and in TCB RSPMCOR of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan (95 patients).

Results. In the stroma and in the zone of tumor infiltration, the number of vessels from 1 to 5 microvessels in the test area was determined as the 1st degree of angiogenesis intensity, the 2nd degree from 6 to 10 microvessels and the 3rd degree more than 11 microvessels. In the area of tumor inflammation, the number of vessels from 1 to 10 microvessels in the test area, 2 degrees from 11 to 20 microvessels, and 3 degrees more than 21 microvessels were determined as the 1st degree of angiogenesis intensity. When analyzing the number of microvessels, we found a close positive relationship between tumor subtypes and the intensity of angiogenesis.

Conclusion. A general pattern was revealed between the intensity of blood

circulation (angiogenesis) of the tumor and its degree of differentiation.